

28

29 ABSTRACT

30

31 EVOO phenolic compounds provide nutritional benefits because of their antioxidant capacity. The
32 interaction between phenolic compounds and proteins may reduce their bioavailability and antioxidant
33 capacity. The objective of this project was to evaluate the interaction between phenolic compounds from
34 EVOO and mucin. EVOO phenolic extract and some commercially available pure phenolic present in
35 EVOO were also used in this study: cinnamic, *p*-coumaric, caffeic, vanillic and protocatechuic acids,
36 Tyrosol, Hydroxytyrosol and oleuropein.

37

38 The interaction between polyphenols and proteins was measured by the increasing of turbidity of the
39 reaction mixture and expressed NTU. Polyphenols solutions at different concentrations were mixed with
40 mucin solutions. Reaction mixtures were measured after 1, 30, 60, 90 and 180 minutes at 37°C.

41

42 The results suggest that EVOO polyphenols interact with the mucin solution forming an insoluble
43 complex after 1 minute of reaction. The highest interaction between polyphenols and proteins was
44 observed for the EVOO phenolic extract and cinnamic, *p*-coumaric and caffeic acids. The interaction
45 between polyphenols and mucin varied depending on the phenols concentration and chemical structure.
46 The importance of the results is to evaluate the possible consequences of EVOO phenolic-protein
47 interactions in the bioavailability and antioxidant capacity of the polyphenols present in the EVOO.

48

49 1. INTRODUCTION

50

51 Virgin olive oil (VOO) is one of the most well-known elements of the Mediterranean diet. It is
52 appreciated because of its nutritional benefits. It contains few, but significant phenolic components that
53 other vegetable oils lack. The phenolic fraction of VOO is formed by a wide range of groups, including
54 phenolic alcohols (hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol), secoiridoid derivatives (dialdehydic and aldehydic form
55 of elenolic acid linked to hydroxytyrosol or 3,4-DHPEA-EDA, and the dialdehydic and aldehydic form of
56 elenolic acid linked to tyrosol or *p*-HPEA-EDA), phenolic acids (vanillic and *p*-coumaric acids), lignans
57 (pinoresinol and acetoxypinoresinol) and flavonoids (luteolin and apigenin) [1-7].

58

59 EVOO (Extra Virgin Olive Oil) sensory properties are largely affected by its phenolic composition.
60 Phenolics are responsible for the bitter and pungent sensory attributes [8-11]. They also provides
61 protection against oxidative process [12, 13]. VOO phenolic compounds show biological activities as
62 inhibition of platelet aggregation [14], inhibition of low density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation [15, 16],
63 anti-inflammatory activities [17], antimicrobial and antiviral activities, immune system regulation [18],

64 protection against oxidative stress [19-21], stimulation of induction of antioxidant enzymes and
65 modulation of the metabolism [22].

66

67 In general, polyphenols are known to interact with protein molecules creating soluble or insoluble
68 complexes; this interaction could be a reversible process. However, it has been shown that interactions
69 salivary proteins with tannins form complexes insoluble non-reversible [23]. These interactions are made
70 through hydrogen binding, hydrophobic or hydrophilic interactions, or less frequently covalent bonds [24-
71 28]. The interactions between polyphenols and proteins can be divided into three steps. First, proteins and
72 polyphenols are combined to form soluble complexes. Then, these complexes can grow to a colloidal
73 size, at which point they scatter light. Finally, they become larger until they form insoluble aggregates
74 [23, 29, 30]. Polyphenol-protein interactions depend on several factors such as: chemical structure of
75 polyphenols, structure of proteins, the protein/polyphenol ratio and some solution parameters (pH, ionic
76 strength, temperature) [27, 31-35].

77

78 Most of the studies on interaction between phenolic compounds and proteins have been focused on
79 tannins with protein precipitating properties. Most of research on tannin- salivary protein interaction has
80 been linked to its role in astringency perception. Tannins interact with proline-rich proteins of saliva
81 producing their precipitation, giving a dry mouth sensation that is referred to as astringency [36-39].
82 Another food technological effect of phenolic-protein interactions is haze formation in beer, fruit juice
83 and wine [25].

84

85 Furthermore, the formation of polyphenol-protein aggregates causes an unfolding of the protein structure
86 and also affects the bioavailability of both components proteins and polyphenols [40, 41]. This reduction
87 in polyphenol bioavailability is also expected to affect their beneficiary properties. The interaction
88 between salivary proteins and polyphenols affects the antioxidant capacity of the low molecular weight
89 polyphenols such as ferulic acid, caffeic acid and catechin [42]. In addition, polyphenols are known to
90 mix with digestive enzymes leading to enzymatic activity modulation [43].

91

92 Few studies have been reported about low molecular weight polyphenols and phenolic compounds
93 present in virgin olive oil. Therefore, the aim of this work was to evaluate the interaction between
94 phenolic of EVOO and mucin (protein rich in threonine, serine and hydroxyproline). EVOO phenolic
95 extract and some commercially available pure phenolic present in VOO were also used in this study:
96 cinnamic, p-coumaric, caffeic, vanillic and protocatechuic acids, tyrosol (p-hydroxyphenylethanol),
97 hydroxytyrosol (3, 4-dihydroxyphenylethanol) and oleuropein. The importance of the results will let to
98 evaluate the possible consequences of EVOO phenolic-mucin interactions in the bioavailability and
99 antioxidant capacity of the polyphenols present in the EVOO.

100

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Samples

2.1.1 EVOO phenolic extract and pure phenolics compounds:

The phenolic extract of VOO was obtained from 'Picual' olive cultivar in the experimental oil mill located in the Centre IFAPA "Venta del Llano". The polyphenol extract was obtained by liquid/liquid extraction with methanol-water (60:40 v/v). A sample of 100 g of EVOO was dissolved in n-hexane (50 mL). The phenolic compounds were extracted with 50 mL of methanol/water four times, mixing at 14.000 rpm during 1.30 min and then, it was left to decant. All the hydroalcoholic fractions were filtered (0.45 µm syringe filter) and then concentrated by lyophilization and reconstituted in methanol (400 µL) for phenolic compounds analysis and in ethanol (50% v/v) to evaluate the interaction with mucin.

Cinnamic, *p*-coumaric, caffeic, vanillic and protocatechuic acids (Sigma-Aldrich), tyrosol (Lancaster Chemicals), hydroxytyrosol, oleuropein (Extrasynthese) were selected as pure phenolics compounds.

Phenolic solutions were prepared by dissolving phenolic extract of EVOO or each pure phenolic compound in 1% ethanol. All samples were prepared immediately prior to testing. Solutions were prepared at the following concentrations: extract of EVOO - 80, 150 and 300 mg/L; pure phenolic compounds - 0, 80, 100, 200, 400, 500, 600, 800 and 1000 mg/L;

2.1.2 Characterization of EVOO phenolic extract:

Total phenol content was determined in EVOO extract following the method described by Vázquez-Roncero, (1973) [44]: using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and absorbance measurement at 725 nm in a Uv-Vis spectrophotometer Cary 50 Bio (Varian, Spain). The results were obtained as mean values of at least three determinations and expressed as mg/kg of caffeic acid.

HPLC Analysis of Phenolic compounds were performed using an HP 1100 series (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA), equipped with a binary pump delivery system, a degasser, an autosampler, a diode array UV-Visible detector and a mass spectrometer detector. A reversed-phase C18 Zorbax Eclipse Plus (150 x 4.6 mm, 1.8 µm particle sizes) with a C18 precolumn filter was used with an injection volume of 20 µL and a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min. The mobile phase was a mixture of water/acetic acid (0.55% v/v) (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B). Solvent gradient changed according to the following conditions: from 0 to 10 min, 95%A: 5%B, from 10 to 12 min, 70%A: 30%B, from 12 to 17 min 67%A: 33%B, from 17 to 20 min 62%A: 38%B, from 20 to 23 min 50%A: 50%B, from 23 to 23.5 min 5%A: 95%B, and from 23.5 to 25 min 0%A: 100%B. The wavelengths were set at 240, 280, and 330 nm. The identification was made

139 using *MS* (Bruker Daltonic, Bremen, Germany) as well. The analyses were carried out employing an
140 electrospray interface (ESI) (G1607A, Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA), operating in positive mode
141 following these conditions: drying gas flow, 9 L/min; nebulizer pressure, 30 psi; drying gas temperature,
142 300°C; capillary voltage, 3200 V; and fragmentor voltage, 70 V. Phenolic compounds were quantified at
143 280 nm, on the basis of the corresponding standard, with the exception of elenolic acid, which were
144 quantified as hydroxytyrosol, and secoiridoid derivatives, which were quantified as oleuropein. The
145 results were obtained as mean values of three determinations and expressed as mg/kg of VOO.

146

147 2.2 Polyphenol-mucin interaction assay

148

149 Polyphenol-mucin interaction assay was carried out according to the method described by Monteleone et
150 al. (2004) [45]. Polyphenols solutions (8 mL) were mixed with 2 mL of mucin from porcine stomach type
151 III (Sigma Aldrich, M1778) solution at 0.2% using a citrate phosphate buffer pH 3.5, 0.1M. Two
152 reference samples were used, a polyphenol solution (8 mL of polyphenol solution mixed with 2 mL of
153 citrate phosphate buffer) and a mucin reference sample (8 mL of 1% ethanol mixed with 2 mL of mucin
154 solution). All the reagents were thermo-stated at 37°C.

155

156 The interaction between the phenolic compounds and the mucin was measured applying the nephelometry
157 method [45, 46]. The turbidity values of the mixes were measured using a portable turbidimeter HACH
158 2100P ISO (Hach Co.) in Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU), from 0.01 to 1000 NTU in automatic
159 range mode and automatic decimal point placement. The ratio optical system includes an LED lamp, a
160 90° detector to monitor the scattered light and a transmitted light detector. The microprocessor calculates
161 the ratio of the signals from the 90° detector and the transmitted light detector. The instrument was
162 calibrated before the experiment with Hach StablCal Stabilized Formazin. The measurements were made
163 with the signal average mode on, which takes ten measurements and calculates their average.

164

165 Each phenol solution mixed with mucin was measured after 1, 30, 60 and 180 min. The polyphenol-
166 mucin interaction was expressed as NTU, obtaining the NTU values measured for the mucin reference
167 (NTUm) plus the polyphenol reference sample (NTUp) from the NTU value of the polyphenol-mucin
168 sample (NTUs), so: $NTU = NTUs - (NTUm + NTUp)$.

169

170 2.3 Data Analysis

171

172 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out in order to evaluate the effects of reaction time and
173 concentration of phenolic compounds on polyphenol-protein interaction. The comparison of means was
174 done by Fisher test (LSD) at a level of significance of 0.05.

175

176

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of EVOO phenolic extract

The lyophilized phenolic extract of virgin olive oil looked like syrup and showed a dark brown color. The total phenol content of the extract was 558 ± 0.01 mg/kg. The composition of the EVOO phenolic extract is shown in Fig. 1. The extract contained the most representative phenolic compounds of virgin olive oil. The main phenolics quantified were isomers of oleuropein aglycone (OA) and isomers of ligustroside aglycone (Lig Agly), secoiridoids derivatives from oleuropein and ligustroside, respectively (Table 1).

3.2 Polyphenol-mucin interaction assay

The relative affinity of EVOO polyphenols to bind with mucin was measured according to their ability to precipitate them in a solution in which the composition of the resulting polyphenol-mucin aggregate was determined directly by nephelometry. This analytical method allows measuring the scattered light in the solution resulting from the gradual formation of a turbidity precipitate corresponding to the polyphenol-mucin aggregate [47].

3.2.1 Effect of reaction time on polyphenol-mucin interaction

The assayed phenolic compounds interacted with mucin resulting in a cloudy solution and then, solution turbidity was higher. An analysis of two-way ANOVA (reaction time and concentration of phenolic compounds) was performed in order to compare the interaction of each phenolic compound (at each concentration) with mucin during a reaction time from 1 to 180 min. Results showed a significant and positive effect of the reaction time on the interaction of VOO phenolic extract, caffeic acid, cinnamic acid, vanilic acid, hydroxytyrosol and oleuropein with mucin ($p \leq 0.05$) (Table 2). Significant differences along the reaction time were obtained for the comparison of mean turbidity values of each phenolic compound applying the LSD test, $n=5$ (Fig. 2).

In general, the mixes of phenolic compounds and mucin showed turbidity immediately after 1 minute. An increase up to maximum was observed during the incubation time, reaching the equilibrium later. Then, a slight decrease was observed for pure compounds. EVOO phenolic extract showed a linear increase of turbidity during the incubation time studied (180 min). Previous works have reported that the turbidity of protein-polyphenol mixes was developed almost instantaneously and then, it increased slightly during the incubation time, reaching the equilibrium for 60 min [31, 45]. The slight decrease of turbidity of some of the pure phenolic after reaching the maximum value may be explained because polyphenol-mucin complexes started to agglomerate, becoming unstable and producing their precipitation and consequently

214 differences in haze value. Therefore, according to Monteleone et al. (2004) a short reaction time was
215 adopted (1 min) in which only aggregates could have been formed [45].

216

217 *3.2.2 Effect of phenolic concentration on polyphenol-mucin interaction*

218

219 In agreement to literature, polyphenol-protein aggregate formation depends of several factors among them
220 the protein and polyphenol concentration on the solution [23, 27, 39, 45, 48]. It can be explained
221 following the model described by Siebert et al. (1996): considering that each polyphenol molecule has a
222 fixed number of binding ends and each protein has a fixed number of polyphenol binding sites. Then, at
223 low polyphenol concentrations respect to protein, each molecule of phenol could form a bridge between
224 two protein molecules, forming dimers of protein, small aggregates and a slight turbidity. When the
225 number of phenol ends equals the number of protein binding sites, each molecule of phenol bind other
226 dimers of protein resulting on largest network of large aggregates complex and increased turbidity. An
227 excess of polyphenols relative to protein would cause all the protein binding sites were occupied;
228 forming small aggregates due to that each free polyphenol end would have small chances of finding a free
229 binding site on a protein molecule and not would form bridge between protein molecules. This would
230 result in less turbidity. Therefore, turbidity is a function of polyphenol- mucin aggregate that depends on
231 the concentration of polyphenols respect to the protein [27].

232

233 In this work, the mucin concentration was constant and chosen taking into consideration the amount used
234 in the artificial formulations [49] versus an increasing polyphenol concentration, for to establish the
235 minimum polyphenol concentration that forming aggregates with mucin. In order to discuss the final
236 results easily, the phenolic compounds were grouped according to their chemical structure as follows:
237 cinnamic acid derivatives, benzoic acid derivatives, phenolic alcohols, secoiridoids and EVOO phenolic
238 extract. The results of two- way ANOVA analysis showed a significant effect of increasing phenolic
239 concentration on mixes turbidity ($p \leq 0.05$, $n=5$) (Table 3).

240

241 For the first minute (1 min) of reaction, the turbidity appeared at different concentrations depending on
242 the phenolic molecular structure. Aggregates with mucin were formed from the lowest concentration (80
243 mg/kg) for *p*-coumaric acid, cinnamic acid and EVOO phenolic extract. Caffeic and vanillic acids
244 produced aggregates from 100 mg/kg whereas for tyrosol, the lowest concentration for turbidity was 200
245 mg/kg. For other phenols such as protocatechuic acid, hydroxytyrosol and oleuropein the turbidity
246 appeared from 400 mg/kg. After the initial increase, many of them achieved equilibrium, although the
247 oleuropein showed a slight final decrease (Fig. 3). These differences could be explained by molecular
248 structure of pure phenolic compounds and the components of EVOO phenolic extract, which determine
249 the formation of large aggregates with different sizes and thus, with different turbidity [45].

250

251 3.2.3 Influence of phenolic compound

252

253 When the effect of the concentration of phenolic compounds was analyzed in the analysis of variance
254 (ANOVA), significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$, $n=5$) were found among the phenolic compounds (Table 3).
255 Comparing the mean turbidity generated by each phenolic compound (LSD test) significant differences
256 was found among them (Fig. 4).

257

258 The VOO phenolic extract exhibited the highest value of turbidity, followed by cinnamic acid derivatives
259 and oleuropein, whereas benzoic acid derivatives and phenyl alcohols showed the lowest. The highest
260 interaction of VOO phenolic extract with mucin may be explained taking into account that their main
261 phenols were oleuropein aglycone and lygustroside aglycone. These compounds have a higher molecular
262 weight, a greater number of aromatic rings and more -OH groups than the individual phenolic
263 compounds used in this study. These are some features of polyphenol structure and properties reported
264 that influence to their capacity of protein binding [28, 30, 31, 50-53]. Pripp et al. (2005) described that
265 hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol of the EVOO extract showed a weakly binding to the proteins, whereas other
266 phenolic compounds of the extract had a stronger binding to BSA and sodium caseinate [54].

267

268 Within the individual phenolic compounds, phenolic-mucin interactions were higher with caffeic, *p*-
269 coumaric and cinnamic acid. This may be due the number of hydroxyl groups and functional groups.
270 Interactions between low molecular weight phenolics and proteins, using G-50 Sephadex
271 Chromatography, were higher for phenolic compounds that contain *o*-dihydroxyl groups such as
272 protocatechuic and caffeic acids [55]. Furthermore, the compounds that contain *o*-dihydroxyl-phenolic
273 groups can be mixed with the protein via a bi-dentate hydrogen bond with an isolated group of hydroxyl-
274 phenolic [35].

275

276 Although oleuropein has a higher molecular weight, two -OH groups and a higher number of aromatic
277 rings, its interaction with mucin may be affected by the glycosidic group of the molecule which may
278 compete with phenol for binding the protein and thus, affect to particle size evolution [56].

279

280 4. CONCLUSIONS

281

282 The nephelometry method was used to quickly and easily determine the interaction between phenolic
283 compounds present in VOO and mucin. All the phenolic assayed interacted with mucin from the
284 beginning of the reaction forming insoluble complexes. The interaction increased during the incubation
285 time to reach equilibrium. Polyphenol-mucin aggregate formation depended on the phenolic
286 concentration and phenol molecular structure. Among the pure phenolic compounds studied, cinnamic

287 acid derivatives showed the highest interaction with mucin. *P*-coumaric and cinnamic acids bound to
288 mucin at low concentrations. VOO phenolic extract showed a higher interaction with mucin than the
289 individual compounds, even at very low concentration. This difference was related to its phenolic
290 composition (secoiridoid derivates and elenolic acid mainly), its molecular weight, functional groups, the
291 number of hydroxyl groups, the position of the phenols in the molecule and interaction between them.

292 The results about formation of polyphenol-mucin complex are important from the nutritional aspect since
293 it could affect the bioavailability and antioxidant capacity of the different phenolic compounds during the
294 digestion of VOO. Furthermore, the binding of polyphenols with digestive enzymes could make the
295 EVOO intake had a modulating effect of digestion. Secondly, the results have shown that the method
296 used in this study to evaluate the polyphenol-protein interaction is fast and easy for its possible
297 application as a complementary method to sensorial analysis to determine the astringency intensity of the
298 EVOO.

299

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461 TABLES

462 **Table 1. Phenolic Composition (mg/kg) of lyophilized VOO phenolic extract measure by HPLC at 280 nm**
463 **(mean \pm SD, n = 3)**
464

Name	Peak No.	mg/kg of VOO
Phenyl alcohols		
Hydroxytyrosol	3	10.98 \pm 0.09
Tyrosol	2	12.22 \pm 0.22
Phenolic Acids		
Gallic Acid	1	1.26 \pm 0.09
Elenoic Acid ^a	6	65.98 \pm 1.76
Caffeic Acid	4	0.27 \pm 0.00
p-cumaric acid	5	0.31 \pm 0.00
Secoiridoid derivatives^b		
Isomers of Oleuropein Aglycone	7, 8, 13, 15, 17, 18, 19	296.41 \pm 2.5
Isomers of ligustroside aglycone	10, 12, 14, 20, 21	194.05 \pm 2.8
Lignans		
Pinoresinol	11	3.9 \pm 0.09
Flavonoids		
Luteolin	9	4.62 \pm 0.01
Apigenine	16	2.98 \pm 0.12

465 ^a Quantified as hydroxytyrosol.

466 ^b Quantified as oleuropein.

467

468 **Table 2. Two way ANOVA analysis of turbidity produced of each phenolic compound (at each concentration)**
 469 **with the mucin during reaction time of 1 at 180 min (n=5)**

470

Origin of variations	F- value	Probability	Critical value for F	Significant difference <i>P<0.005</i>
VOO Phenolic Extract	3.795	0.032	3.259	Yes
Caffeic acid	5.026	0.003	2.668	Yes
<i>p</i> -coumaric acid	2.298	0.080	2.668	NO
Cinnamic acid	2.877	0.038	2.668	Yes
Protocatecuic acid	2.520	0.060	2.668	NO
Vanillic acid	3.795	0.012	2.668	Yes
Hydroxytyrosol	13.611	0.000	2.668	Yes
Tyrosol	1.713	0.171	2.668	NO
Oleuropein	2.967	0.034	2.668	Yes

471

472

473 **Table 3. Two way ANOVA analysis of turbidity of phenolic compounds (at each concentration) at 1 min of**
 474 **reaction whit mucin (n=5)**
 475

Origen of variations	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average of Squares	F- value	Probability	Critical value for F	Significant difference <i>P<0.005</i>
Concentration	359.3265424	8	44.9158178	18.82702991	2.4116E-13	2.108688484	Yes
Phenolic Compounds	99.97715556	7	14.28245079	5.986668873	3.14392E-05	2.178155555	Yes
Error	133.5997132	56	2.385709164				
Total	592.9034111	71					

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477 FIGURE 1

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488 FIGURE 3

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496 FIGURE CAPTIONS

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498 **Figure 1. HPLC chromatogram VOO phenolic extract (280, 240 and 330 nm)**

499 Peak identification numbers: 1. Gallic Acid ; 2. Tyrosol; 3. Hydroxytyrosol; 4. Caffeic Acid; 5. p-
500 cumaric acid; 6. Elenoic Acid; 7, 8, 13, 15, 17, 18 y 19. Isomers of oleuropein aglycone ; 9. Luteolin; 10,
501 12, 14, 20 y 21. Isomers of ligustroside aglycone; 11. Pinosesinol; 16. Apigenine.

502

503

504 **Figure 2. Turbidity (NTU) of polyphenol - mucin mixes as function of reaction time**

505 Values are the mean of concentration. Fisher test (LSD) has been used to assess significance. Different
506 letters in the same group indicate significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the reaction time, $n=5$.

507

508 **Figure 3. Turbidity (NTU) of polyphenol-mucin complex as a function of the concentration of**
509 **polyphenol compound in 1 minute of reaction**

510

511 **Figure 4. Turbidity (NTU) of polyphenol-mucin complex for 1 minute of reaction**

512 Values are the mean of the concentration, $n=5$. Fisher test (LSD) has been used to assess significance.

513 Different letters indicate significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$ - LSD value 1.45).

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